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GROUP ACTIVITIES WITH AI TEACHER SUPPORT IN PBL EDUCATION

Mikiko Sode Tanaka¹

International College of Technology
Kanazawa, Japan

Takao Ito, Masako Shin and Keisuke Miyazaki²

Kanazawa Institute of Technology
Nonoichi, Japan

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ABSTRACT

We have built a system that supports PBL education called “AI teacher”, and are currently verifying the effects in actual classes. In this paper, we will introduce the mechanism and effect of group activities supported by “AI teacher” which is a part of the system in PBL education.

From 2020, because of COVID-19, we had to do online PBL education with the online communication tools like Zoom. The problem at this time was that when the students were divided into multiple groups and did group work in breakout rooms of Zoom, the teacher could not grasp the situation of the students. Teachers can check by entering the breakout room of each group in turn, but they cannot see the whole students at once. This was a big difference from face-to-face education. Therefore, we introduced the system which possible to check the student's remarks by utilizing the system that automatically records the conversation in the breakout rooms. This allowed teachers to see the progress of each group. Teachers took the initiative and could advice students who did not participate in the activity well.

In this paper, we will explain the system configuration that automatically documents the conversation, and explain effect of utilization of the system and problems. In addition, we will explain the overall configuration and mechanism of the “AI teacher”. “AI teacher” use Slack to manage the progress of group activities and provide advice. “AI teacher” is the system that records the conversation as a document, automatically

¹ Mikiko Sode Tanaka

sode@neptune.kanazawa-it.ac.jp

² Takao Ito, Masako Shin and Keisuke Miyazaki

ito@neptune.kanazawa-it.ac.jp

participates in group conversations and gives advice. Also, students can check that they wondered with the AI chatbot.

1 PBL EDUCATION IN EXTRACURRICULAR CLASSES

Industry requests the higher education for the engineer development education which is acquire skills, attitudes, patience, spontaneity, creativity, craftsmanship, leadership, motivation, and teamwork. CDIO is a concept devised by the Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT) in the United States and three universities in Sweden to respond to this reform of engineering education. CDIO is an abbreviation for Conceive, Design, Implement, and Operate, and is called the "CDIO Initiative," which consists of the "CDIO syllabus" and the "CDIO standard". It aims for high quality education through the framework using real-world systems and products[1].

Our schools have been conducting the CDIO education since 2010. At first, it was introduced in Project Design course (PD), which is regular class [2, 3]. Figure 1 shows the PD educational class at Kanazawa Institute of Technology(KIT). Our school defines five stages as engineering design processes. PD1 is a class for learning problem discovery, problem clarification, and idea creation, and PD2 is a class for learning idea creation, idea evaluation and careful selection, and concrete implementation of ideas. Evaluating PD education at our school from a CDIO perspective, it corresponds to C: conceive and D: design. At our schools, we teach C: conceive and D: design in regular classes, and we teach I: Implement and O: Operate in extracurricular classes [4, 5].

Engineering Curriculum \ CDIO	Finding a problem	Clarification of the problem	Creation of ideas	Evaluation and selection of ideas	Materialization of ideas
Conceive	1st year Project design 1		2nd year Project design 2		
Design					

Fig. 1. Engineering classes of KIT

1.1 The e-Syllabus to support student learning

Since KIT launched the e-Syllabus in 2016, the teachers have been utilizing the e-Syllabus as one of communication tools with students. The e-syllabus shows the lesson content for each week and tells students what to prepare and what to review. Also, e-Syllabus provides teaching materials and collecting reports. Some of teachers have been using the e-Syllabus when carrying out flipped learning and active learning [6]. Figure 2 is an example of the e-Syllabus of PD2. The e-Syllabus is displayed, if a

student logs in to his page from the portal site, opens his list of courses and click the course. The e-Syllabus displays the contents of learning of weekly classes with the guide of learning targets, scholastic evaluation method, and preferred achievement, etc. Students can check the content of each week's study, prepare for the class, and attend the class. Also, if the class is conducted online, it will be listed here, such as the Zoom (videotelephony software program) participation URL.

The e-Syllabus is a powerful tool when carrying out flipped learning and active learning. It was used as the main platform of the on-line education under the state of emergency of COVID-19. Important information such as "Will classes be held or will they be canceled?", "Will it a face-to-face class or Will classes be held online?", was sent from the e-Syllabus.

Fig. 2. The example of e-Syllabus

The flow of one class in the PD is explained. In the PD class, the faculty members will first give a lecture on today's activities, how to proceed with discussions, and tools that can be used. After the lecture, students are divided in groups and do group work in Zoom Breakout Rooms. Students report the results of group work and the class ends. In face-to-face classes, teachers visually check the situation of each group, call out to groups whose group activities are stagnant, and give guidance. It was difficult to give this instruction in online classes.

After the class, the teacher confirms learning results of the week from the reports. In online classes, we cannot see what the students are discussing in group activities, so we can only see the situation from the post-class report. As a result, it took a long time to recover of the progress, and some groups did not work well.

2 “AI TEACHER” SYSTEM CONFIGURATION AND USAGE

2.1 “AI teacher” system configuration

We have used the GROW model[7] and CLEAR model[8,9] to develop the learning power of students. Figure 3 shows the CLEAR model process. The primary focus of the CLEAR model is to create students that are committed to team plans and are happy to contribute to shared goals, rather than simply complying to managerial demands. It consists of five phases. The contracting stage focusses on establishing desired outcomes – both individual and group – and revealing how the process can be tailored to be most valuable to the individual’s needs. The key aspects of listening stage are ‘active listening’ that aim to allow the coach and individual to truly understand the situation. Awareness is given on the Exploring stage. The Action stage encourages action. During the Review stage, students will see whether they are on track to reach their goals, asking them to see what’s going on and how to improve. By using the coaching method, the student’s current position and the words of the question at that position are determined, so it is a method that is easy to automate.

Fig. 3. CLEAR model process

We are developing an “AI teacher” that provides PBL (project/problem based learning) education using coaching techniques. Figure 4 shows the overall configuration diagram. Students access to the digital platform and work on the project team database. The AI engine acts as the facilitator on each project using the course materials and know-how database. Text mining and chatbots serve as main components of AI engine.

We decided to use the chat system Slack (communication platform software program) [10] as a interface of “AI teacher”. Slack is excellent in a user interface, and integration with other services is easy. It can be easily accessed from the e-Syllabus. Use of Slack has spread not only among companies but among students because of its ease of use and basically free of charge. A “Channel” can be set up for each project and project members communicate and work in the channel. All of the conversation and produced data are recorded as a searchable team data.

Fig. 4. “AI teacher” configuration

In the proposed system, more than 6,500 reports are stored in the web server as the students output of the four PD courses from 2012 to 2018, that is, about 1,500 PD Introduction experiment reports, 1,700 PD1 design reports, 2,000 PD2 implementation documents and 1,400 PDIO project reports. “AI teacher” use the DB of the web server. The themes of projects are various from an airplane or a car even to sightseeing and food. Keywords are extracted from each report by text mining, and they are given to the answer report as index. There is also the database which teachers prepared the principles and laws of physics and chemistry. Teachers’ instruction materials including PowerPoint class slides are also on the e-Syllabus and the web server. These data can be saved as course materials and used as the know-how database.

The AI engine facilitates project activities instead of teachers. In addition, the AI engine help teachers work. It analyses course materials and know-how data using text mining. It also analyses the ongoing project data in the team database. Matching data from the analyses results, the AI engine recommends the course materials and references to the project. Chatbots are used to answer questions from the students, monitor their activities on the project and give them feedbacks. Chatbots behave like teachers who take charge of the projects.

2.2 “AI teacher” system usage

Chatbots can be used as the virtual facilitators. It will extract keywords in the questions and find related materials which best match the keywords from the database. One example question is, “How can we make a poster of our project?”. The chatbot answers “You can find a template and a sample poster in this link ...” or “You can find some posters relevant to your project here ...”. Such a system will reduce teachers’ work and students can learn with the chatbot.

The “AI teacher” provides a minutes function to solve the following problems that became problems in online classes. We are currently using AmiVoice® (voice recognition AI engine) [11] for this feature.

1. Students need to turn off the microphone when the teacher is speaking because the voices overlap and it is difficult to hear. This made it difficult for teachers to grasp what the students were doing. In addition, it became difficult to visually check the students. For this reason, it became difficult to grasp the degree of understanding of students.
2. When students do group work, each group moves to a breakout room in Zoom for discussion. Teachers cannot join multiple groups at the same time and can only see the status of one team. In the face-to-face class, I was able to visually grasp the situation of each group, but the class by Zoom made it impossible.

The screenshot displays a software interface for creating meeting minutes. At the top, there are controls for audio recording and playback. Below that, a summary section includes 'Attendee list' (山田, 佐藤, 鈴木), 'Meeting time' (2020/11/17 14:00 ~ 14:30), and 'Utterance time' (14:10:59). The 'Speaker' is identified as 山田. The 'Content of remark' is: '前回はメールにて共有をした、新しい製品であるScribeAssistについてのホームページのデザイン案なのですが、こちらについて何かご意見いただけますでしょうか。私の意見なのですがもう少し見出しの文字を大きくしてもらえると区別がつきやすくなって、視覚的によいのではと思いました。カラーバランスについては背景が少し濃いかなと思うので、いくらか薄く整えたほうが文字も見やすく良いのではと思いました。' The interface also shows a 'ToDo' tag and an 'Agenda classification tag'.

Fig. 5. Automatic minutes creation tool

In order to solve these problems, it was decided to introduce a Speech-to-text reporter. Figure 5 shows how the minutes creation tool creates minutes. In real time, the speaker is identified and the spoken content is displayed as a document. The minutes function records all the content discussed in the group. It also records who spoke.

Therefore, you can check the content of the discussion in real time. You can also check who has not participated in the discussion.

3 EVALUATION RESULTS

The minutes function of the “AI teacher” has shed light on the situation where online classes are required due to the influence of COVID-19. It is not possible to automatically record all the contents accurately, but it is possible to make the document at a level where the contents of the proceedings can be confirmed with a little modification by the initial person in charge while discussing. If you manually create the minutes, you will summarize and record the contents of the discussion, but it is effective that you can record all the contents by using this. As you continue to use it, your recognition level will improve and you will have fewer places to work on.

One teacher said it was useful in finding students who couldn't attend the class. In addition, other teachers said that they are suitable for confirming the depth of the discussion because they can know the content of the discussion including the content that was didn't go well.

4 CONCLUSION

We have built a system that supports PBL education called “AI teacher”, and are currently verifying the effects in actual classes.

From 2020, because of COVID-19, we had to do online PBL education with the online communication tools like Zoom. The problem at this time was that when the students were divided into multiple groups and did group work in breakout rooms, the teacher could not grasp the situation of the students. Teachers can check by entering the breakout room of each group in turn, but they cannot see the whole at once. This was a big difference from face-to-face education.

Therefore, we used automatical recorder of “AI teacher” that record all conversation in the breakout rooms. This allowed teachers to see the progress of each group, who took the initiative and who did not participate in the activity well. The faculty members who used it said that it is effective because we can confirm who is not participating in the discussion. Other faculty members also said that it was effective to understand the content of the discussion in detail. We have confirmed the effectiveness of this system.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Edward F. Crawley, Johan Malmqvist, Sören Östlund, Doris R. Brodeur, Kristina Edström, "Rethinking Engineering Education," Springer, 2014.

- [2] Ito T., Shin M., Miyazaki K., Iwata, S., & Sentoku, E. 2015. The Effects of Spiral Educational Method through PBL: KIT Project Design Program. In: Proc. of the 43rd Annual SEFI Conference, June 29-July 2, Orleans, France.
- [3] Ito T., Shin M., Miyazaki K., Iwata, S., & Sentoku, E. 2016. The Project Design Education Collaborating with City Governments and Communities. In: Proc. of the 18th International Conference on Engineering & Product Design Education, Sep. 8-9, Aalborg, Denmark.
- [4] Mikiko Sode Tanaka, Keijiro Yamada, Masashi Saito, Takumi Kawamoto, Takao Ito, (2018), System Development Method Education through Regional Collaboration, Journal of JSEE, Vol. 66, Issue 4, pp. 21-26.
- [5] Mikiko Sode Tanaka, Takao Ito, (2021), Develop the Ability to Learn by Extracurricular Activities through Regional Collaboration -Sightseeing Guidance for Overseas Tourists by Using a Share Cycle-, Journal of JSEE, Vol. 69, Issue 2, pp. 15-21.
- [6] Ito T., Ishii K., Nishi M., Shin M. and Miyazaki K. 2019. Comparison of the effects of the integrated learning environments between the social science and the mathematics. In: SEFI 47th Annual Conference, Sep. 16-20, Budapest, Hungary.
- [7] Jonathan Passmore : Excellence in Coaching: The Industry Guide, Kogan Page Ltd, 2015.
- [8] Marie Taylor, Steve Crabb : Business Coaching & Mentoring For Dummies, John Wiley & Sons, 2017.
- [9] Peter Hawkins : Leadership Team Coaching: Developing Collective Transformational Leadership, Kogan Page, 2017.
- [10] Slack, <https://slack.com/intl/ja-jp/>, Access 2021.05.01.
- [11] AmiVoice, <https://www.advanced-media.co.jp/amivoice>, access 2021.05.01.